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APPLICATE

Advanced Prediction in Polar regions and beyond: Modelling, observing system design and Linkages associated with a Changing Arctic climaTE

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**Draft concept for a joint YOPP-
APPLICATE Summer School (including
list of possible co-sponsors)**

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

To meet the growing societal need for young scientists trained in the area of weather and climate prediction, a 10-days Polar Prediction School for early-career scientists from around the world will be held in Spring 2018.

The school will be organised in the frame of the EU-funded APPLICATE project and the World Meteorological Organisation's Polar Prediction Project (PPP) in occasion of the Year of Polar Prediction (YOPP).

Topics of the school will include a combination of polar weather and climate theory lectures with exercises on modelling and field meteorology techniques. Each of these components forms a crucial pillar of the prediction problem, and the motivation for combining these is to provide participants with a complete overview of the components required to understand and predict polar weather.

The Polar Prediction School 2018 will provide quality training for the next generation of polar scientists, training materials publicly available and the opportunity for early career scientists to build their networks and to approach senior scientists expert in the field of polar climate.

1. INTRODUCTION

Polar regions are experiencing rapid climate change with consequences for the weather and sea ice. This change is opening up new possibilities for businesses such as tourism, shipping, fisheries, and oil and gas extraction, but also bringing new risks to the delicate polar environments. Effective weather and climate prediction is essential to managing these risks; however, our ability to forecast polar environmental conditions over periods from days to decades ahead falls far behind our abilities in the mid-latitudes. To meet the growing societal need for young scientists trained in this area, a Polar Prediction School for early-career scientists from around the world will be held in Spring 2018.

The school will be organised in the frame of the EU-funded APPLICATE project and the World Meteorological Organisation's Polar Prediction Project (PPP) in occasion of the Year of Polar Prediction (YOPP).

A similar school was held in 2016 (Day et al., 2017), which provides an excellent model, well received by the students.

2. POLAR PREDICTION SCHOOL 2018

2.1. Dates and location

As in 2016, the 2018 school will be held at the Abisko Scientific Research Station (<http://polar.se/en/abisko-naturvetenskapliga-station/>) in northern Sweden.

Tentative dates for the school are 17-27 April 2018, which will be confirmed in early June.

2.2. Topics

Topics of the school will include a combination of polar weather and climate theory lectures with exercises on modelling and field meteorology techniques. Each of these components forms a crucial pillar of the prediction problem, and the motivation for combining these is to provide participants with a complete overview of the components required to understand and predict polar weather.

Focus will be on the Arctic but comparisons with Antarctic will be also shown as well as climate linkages with mid-latitudes.

2.3. Students

The school will be open to 30 early career scientists (PhD students and postdocs) from around the world of which seven places will be reserved for APPLICATE partners.

2.4. Promotion of the school and call for applications

The official call will be issued by APPLICATE and YOPP offices in early June 2017 with deadline for applications in September 2017 and published on APECS, APPLICATE, YOPP websites as well as all participating organisations. A page will be built on the APECS website which will be used as the school's homepage for all information and materials.

In addition to the *Polarprediction* mailing list, the call will be also disseminated to the major polar and climate mailing lists such as *Climlist*, *Cryolist* and *Arctic Info* as well as via social media.

2.5. Student application process

Applicants will apply to the school by sending their curricula along with a cover letter where they will need to include a short description of their research and how this would benefit from the summer school. They will also need to specify if they are early career scientists involved in the APPLICATE project.

2.6. Student selection process

The ranking of applications will be based on relevance of the applicant's research topic and their excellence (relative to the applicant's career stage). Priority will be given to early career scientists. International as well as gender diversity will be also considered in the selection of the students.

2.7. Trainers: selection procedure and preliminary list

Speakers will be invited based on their expertise in the topics of the school. International as well as gender diversity will be carefully considered too in the selection of the speakers.

The list of trainers from last the 2016 school (Table 1) composes a preliminary list for the school from which the organisers will start drawing potential instructors. Trainers will be confirmed by the end of 2017.

Table 1: Preliminary list of speakers

Name	Organisation
Cecilia Bitz	University of Washington
Ian Brooks	University of Leeds
Matthieu Chevallier	Meteo France
Jonathan Day	University of Reading
Helge Goessling	Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine Research
Thomas Jung	Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine Research
Jennifer Kay	University of Colorado Boulder
Erik Kolstad	Uni Research Climate, Bjerknes Centre for Climate Research
Don Perovich	Cold Regions Research and Engineering Laboratory
James Screen	Exeter University
Gunilla Svensson	Stockholm University

2.8. Training activities: preliminary programme

The programme will include a unique mixture of in lectures and modelling as well as collection and analysis of field observations. A preliminary program, based on that of the 2016 school, is shown in table 2.

Table 2: Preliminary programme of the Polar Prediction School 2018.

		Session				
		AM - 1	AM - 2	PM - 1	PM - 2	Evening
Day of school	1	Welcome	Intro to polar weather	Practical: set up met observations tower		Icebreaker and networking activities
	2	Observations	Intro to polar climate	Predictability	Practical: Predictability	Student research presentations
	3	Initial value ensembles	Practical: Large ensemble	Discussion	Projection uncertainty	Career pathways
	4	See ice in the polar climate system	Sea ice 101	Practical: floe size model	Discussion	Presentation skills
	5	Sea ice modelling	Polar ocean forecasting	Practical: ocean model	Discussion	Abstract boot-camp
	6	Excursion Day				
	7	Practical: working with observations		Diurnal and seasonal cycles	Practical	Education and Outreach skills
	8	Clouds	Polar lows	Practical: Arctic Hurricanes exercise	Discussion	Project management
	9	Mid-latitude/polar linkages	Polar representation in GCMs			Celebration
	10	Wrap up				

2.9. Training materials

Training material available to the students will include lecture presentations, readings, and practical exercises (e.g., model codes).

Templates for Frostbyte videos (30-seconds videos by the students on their research) will be prepared and distributed to the students in advance of the school.

Lectures will be recorded when possible and all training materials will be available on the school’s website after the school has ended.

2.10. Social activities

The programme includes also several social activities including an ice-breaker reception, an excursion and a final celebration. Plenty of opportunity will be available to the students for networking (e.g., coffee breaks and meals) especially between the trainers (senior scientists) and the trainees (early career scientists).

2.11. Expected outcomes/ impact

The Polar Prediction School 2018 will provide:

- Quality training for the next generation of polar scientists.
- Students will produce Frostbyte videos on their research which they can use afterwards also for outreach in their organisations.
- Training materials will be publicly available online for all those interested
- A network of polar early career scientists
- A training assessment with survey on learning experience for APPLICATE final training assessment.

2.12. Budget and sponsors

Funds for the school will come mostly from APPLICATE (€30k allocated within the project) and YOPP (€15k from the Polar Prediction Project trust fund). Additional funds will be sought to contribute towards travel and registration costs for students. A summary of foreseen costs is given in Table 3.

Table 3: Preliminary costs foreseen for the Polar Prediction School 2018.

Expenditure	Cost
Flights for Lectures (average ~900 Euro / person)	9k€
Abisko Station fees (sek)	21k€
Catering	14k€
Travel Stipends	4k€
Equipment transportation/shipping	7k€
Total	55k€

2.13. Organisation of the school

A project manager at the University of Tromsø is being recruited who will be in charge of the school's organisation including logistics. The project manager will be assisted by the school organisers Jonathan Day (University of Reading) and Gerlis Fugmann (University of Tromsø and APECS).

3. ACRONYMS

PPP Polar Prediction Project

YOPP Year of Polar Prediction

4. REFERENCES

Day, J.J., G. Svensson, I.M. Brooks, C. Bitz, L. Broman, G. Carver, M. Chevallier, H. Goessling, K. Hartung, T. Jung, J.E. Kay, E.W. Kolstad, D. Perovich, J. Screen, S. Siemen, and F. Váňa, 2017: The Abisko Polar Prediction School. Bull. Amer. Meteor. Soc., 98, 445–447, doi: 10.1175/BAMS-D-16-0119.1.